
Impact of Education on the Awareness of Financial Planning among Villagers of Satara District

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Abstract:

Financial Planning is a methodical way for achieving life goals. A financial plan serves as a roadmap for navigating life's challenges. The process of financial planning allows an individual to maximize their resources in order to achieve their objectives. It helps people save more money, improves their quality of life, and prepares them for future emergencies. Thirty-three villages in the Satara district were the sites of this investigation. 384 respondents who were chosen by random selection provided the data needed for the study. Numerous statistical tools like frequency, percentage and cross tabulation have been used to evaluate the data that was gathered with the aid of a schedule. The results reveals that respondents who are graduates & post graduates as compared to respondents who are less educated or illiterate have a higher awareness level about financial planning.

Keywords: *Financial Planning, Financial Literacy, Education.*

Introduction:

The process of turning cash into a financial asset is referred to as investment. Purchasing financial instruments with the hopes of earning a profit in the future is referred to as investing. The contemporary Indian financial market offers a wide range of financial products such as bank deposits, gold and silver, real estate, life insurance, postal savings, shares, debentures, mutual funds, derivatives, etc. Investors spend their excess funds in a variety of ways, depending on their awareness, knowledge, goals, risk tolerance, etc.

Every investor has varied goals for their investments including safety, liquidity, tax advantages, maximizing wealth, buying a home, getting married, and raising children. A person prefers to consult with specific individuals such as friends, family, tax consultants, chartered accountants and relatives, for financial advice.

Every person needs to understand financial planning in order to deal with the

various financial products and services available on the market. We must integrate financial literacy into our daily lives. The process of financial planning allows an individual to maximize their resources in order to achieve their objectives. It gives people a higher standard of living, helps them save more money, etc. A person who is sufficiently knowledgeable about financial planning is better able to make wise investment choices.

Review of Literature:

Suchitra A. (March 2016) investigated financial knowledge and investing practices of individuals of Kerala. A systematic questionnaire was used to gather the necessary study data from 150 people in the city and 150 people in the villages. The data were gathered using a stratified random sampling approach. Statistics techniques including frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, ANOVA test, and t test were used to examine the collected

information. According to the research, respondents' awareness levels were somewhat above average. The survey revealed that newspapers and television were the primary information sources for investors. The majority of urban investors, however, depend on financial experts. According to the study's findings, investors' levels of knowledge fluctuate significantly depending on their age, gender, educational background, and home area.

Prabhat Poorna (November 2016) studied the impact of risk on the investment decisions and relationship between various factors with the risk taking ability of the investors. 100 investors from the Vijayawada region completed a questionnaire to provide the primary data for the study. With the use of statistical methods like frequency and percentage, the information collected was examined. The association between various parameters and investors' capacity for risk-taking was investigated using the Chi square test. The study discovered that important determinants on investing decisions were age, gender, income, educational background and occupation. The capacity of the investors to take risks was independent to their gender or age. It was discovered that an investor's capacity for taking risks was correlated with their employment, income, and level of education.

Chaurasia Pratibha (July 2017) undertook a research to determine the investment preferences of investors in the Indore district and to examine the effects of various demographic factors on those choices. The samples were chosen using the judgement sampling approach. 229 investors' responses to a questionnaire were used to collect data, which was then examined using statistical methods including frequency, percentage, and chi square test. The study revealed that investors favored fixed deposits over capital markets as their preferred investment instrument. It was discovered that the

demographic characteristics of investors, such as their age, gender, and educational background, significantly influenced their investing preferences. It was proposed to run financial planning workshops and awareness campaigns.

Importance of the Study:

Every individual wishes to invest money in order to generate a profit and put money to good use. The primary occupation of the villagers of Satara district is farming and related activities. Their investing options are limited due to low and uncertain income, a lack of education and skills, and so on. Different investment alternatives appeal to people of various ages, education levels, genders, income levels, and family structures. The villagers' investment decisions vary depending on demographic parameters as well as their awareness of financial planning. This study has been carried out in the villages of the Satara district of Maharashtra. This study makes it possible to learn about the level of awareness of financial planning among village investors based on their educational qualification.

Statement of Research Problem:

As a growing country, India faces the daunting task of obtaining sufficient funds for its development projects. Many scholars, economists, and decision-makers have observed that demographic factors impact the investment choices of individual investors.

To make informed investment decisions, a person must be aware of every potential opportunity available to them. The aim of the current study is to undertake a thorough analysis of the awareness of the village investors about the financial planning based on their educational qualification. The study is intended to provide detailed answers to the following two questions:

1. What is the concept of financial planning?
2. What is the impact of Education on the awareness about financial planning?

Objectives of the Study:

The present study intends to achieve the following objectives:

- 1) To overview the concept of financial planning.
- 2) To examine the impact of education on the awareness about financial planning.

Scope of the Study:

The geographical scope of this research is limited to the villages in the Satara district. Satara district consists of 11 talukas. The survey included three villages from each taluka, chosen at random. Thus, this study is limited to 33 villages in Satara district.

The conceptual scope is confined to determining awareness of financial planning. The analytical scope is confined to examining obtained data using statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, and cross tabulation.

Research Methodology:

Type of Research: It is a descriptive research.

Data Sources: Primary data has been collected from villager investors using a standardized schedule. The secondary information has been acquired from secondary sources such as books, journals, and reports.

Instrument: The schedule is divided into two parts: Investor Demographic Profile and Awareness of Financial Planning. The data for the inquiry has been collected using a five-point Likert scale. The awareness of financial planning has been tested using 20 statements.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Awareness of individuals about financial planning depends upon their educational qualification. Following frequency distribution Table No. 1 shows the distribution of respondents on the basis of educational qualification.

Table No. 1 Classification of Respondents as per Qualification

Sr. No.	Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
1	Illiterate	89	23.18
2	Less than SSC	93	24.22
3	SSC	26	6.77
4	HSC	53	13.80
5	Diploma	18	4.69
6	Graduation	77	20.05
7	Post-Graduation	28	7.29
	Total	384	100

(Source: Primary Data Compiled by Researcher)

The above Table No. 1 shows that, the respondents possess different types of educational qualifications. Out of total respondents, 93 respondents i.e. 24.22 % respondents have education less than SSC, followed by 89 respondents i.e. 23.18 % respondents are illiterate, followed by 77 respondents i.e. 20.05 % respondents are graduates. Out of total respondents, only

4.69 % respondents are diploma holders, 6.77 % respondents are SSC pass out and 7.29 % respondents are post graduates. The percentage clearly indicates that, more than 60 % of total respondents have educational qualification up to HSC only. It indicates that, majority of the village people of Satara district are less educated.

Awareness of Respondents on the basis of Education Qualification:

Five variables namely Money Management, Investment Planning, Estate Planning, Insurance Planning, and Retirement Planning have been identified as being relevant for gauging the financial planning awareness of village investors in the Satara district. The five-point Likert scale was used to collect the data needed for the investigation. Each variable has 4 statements. It means the maximum total

score of 1 variable is 20. It means the maximum total score of all 5 variables is 100. The total scores of respondents have been classified into 3 categories namely; Low Awareness, Average Awareness and High Awareness. Following frequency distribution Table No. 2 shows the classification of respondents into Low Awareness, Average Awareness and High Awareness on the basis of educational qualification.

Table No. 2 Awareness of Respondents on the basis of Education Qualification

Educational Qualification * TotalAwareness1 Cross tabulation						
			TotalAwareness1			Total
			Low Awareness	Avg. Awareness	High Awareness	
Edu. Qua.	Illiterate	Count	73	16	0	89
		% within Edu. Qua.	82.0%	18.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	Less than SSC	Count	53	39	1	93
		% within Edu. Qua.	57.0%	41.9%	1.1%	100.0%
	SSC	Count	4	16	6	26
		% within Edu. Qua.	15.4%	61.5%	23.1%	100.0%
	HSC	Count	4	27	22	53
		% within Edu. Qua.	7.5%	50.9%	41.5%	100.0%
	Diploma	Count	0	7	11	18
		% within Edu. Qua.	0.0%	38.9%	61.1%	100.0%
	Graduation	Count	2	15	60	77
		% within Edu. Qua.	2.6%	19.5%	77.9%	100.0%
	Post Graduation	Count	0	1	27	28
		% within Edu. Qua.	0.0%	3.6%	96.4%	100.0%
Total		Count	136	121	127	384
		% within Edu. Qua.	35.4%	31.5%	33.1%	100.0%

(Source: Compiled by Researcher)

According to the above table, 89 out of the 384 respondents are illiterate. Out of this, majority i.e. 82 % respondents has low awareness and remaining 18 % respondents has average awareness about financial planning.

Out of total 384 respondents, 93 respondents have education less than SSC. Out of this, majority i.e. 57 % respondents has low awareness, followed by 41.9 % respondents with average awareness and remaining 1.1 % respondents has high awareness about financial planning.

26 respondents out of the 384 total respondents hold an SSC qualification. Out of this, majority i.e. 61.5 % respondents has average awareness, followed by 23.1 % respondents with high awareness and remaining 15.4 % respondents has low awareness about financial planning.

Out of total 384 respondents, 53 respondents have education of HSC. Out of this, majority i.e. 50.9 % respondents has average awareness, followed by 41.5 % respondents with high awareness and

remaining 7.5 % respondents has low awareness about financial planning.

Out of total 384 respondents, 18 respondents Diploma holders. Out of this, majority i.e. 61.1 % respondents has high awareness and remaining 38.9 % respondents has average awareness about financial planning.

Out of total 384 respondents, 77 respondents are graduates. Out of this, majority i.e. 77.9 % respondents has high awareness, followed by 19.5 % respondents with average awareness and remaining 2.6

Findings:

1. Maximum i.e. 24.22 % respondents have education less than SSC, followed by 23.18 % illiterates and 20.05 % graduates. Out of total respondents, only 4.69 % respondents are diploma holders, 6.77 % respondents are SSC pass out and 7.29 % respondents are post graduates. It indicates that most of the respondents of the study area possess limited educational qualifications. (Table No. 1)
2. Based on the educational background, those with post-graduate, graduate and diploma degrees have a high level of awareness of financial planning, while those with no education or education below the SSC have a low level of awareness. (Table No. 2)
3. Out of 28 post graduate respondents majority i.e. 96.4 % respondents has high awareness and out of 77 graduate respondents, majority i.e. 77.9 % respondents has high awareness about financial planning. (Table No. 2)
4. Out of 89 illiterate respondents majority i.e. 82 % respondents has low awareness and out of 93 respondents having education less than SSC majority i.e. 57 % respondents has low awareness about financial planning. It indicates that, the awareness level of individual investor's increases with increase in educational qualification. (Table No. 2)

% respondents has low awareness about financial planning.

Out of total 384 respondents, 28 respondents are post graduates. Out of this, majority i.e. 96.4 % respondents has high awareness and remaining 3.6 % respondents has low awareness about financial planning.

The table makes it clearly evident that the respondents' level of education has an impact on their awareness of financial planning. In comparison to individuals with lower educational qualifications, those with higher qualifications are more aware of financial planning.

Suggestions:

1. The "New India Literacy Programme" (NILP), a program authorized by the Central Government of India in 2022, should be implemented by the state government in order to increase literacy among the illiterate people in every village who are at least 15 years old.
2. A number of articles about financial planning, investment options, and financial literacy should be published by the newspaper agencies. To raise people's level of awareness & knowledge, the articles should be released on a regular basis on a designated day.
3. To teach parents and village residents about financial literacy, financial planning, investment options, etc., the schools and colleges in the villages should host special talks. These kinds of initiatives need to be planned during social events like annual functions and parent meetings.
4. In order to teach the village residents about financial literacy, financial planning, investment options, etc., the colleges and universities should organize events such as guest lectures, street plays, dramas, skits, etc. during the NSS camps and make sure that the majority of the village residents attend.

Conclusion:

This study has been conducted to measure the awareness level of village investors about financial planning based on their educational qualification. The cross-tabulation results reveals that respondents who are graduates & post graduates as compared to respondents who are less educated or illiterate have a higher awareness level about financial planning.

The study concludes that, there is a need to increase the financial literacy of the village peoples. It can be achieved through conducting financial literacy camps, organizing special lectures on financial literacy, publishing series of articles in the local newspapers etc.

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